

Mitigation Techniques for Virtualization Related Security Threats

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Abstract: Cloud computing is a new and innovative way which offers efficient and flexible ways in which businesses can access services that are crucial in this rapidly developing environment. This is a very cost effective measure as the infrastructure use in cloud is shared and it comes at a cheaper cost as compared to the traditional approaches. However, there may be various security issues and breaches in privacy which may affect the integrity of these services thereby rendering them dangerous for use by organizations without special measures taken to safeguard this form of computing. As cloud computing applications rise, so does the apparent threats go up. There are not many research papers that deal with cloud security exclusively and many of them are partial either dealing with virtualization related security breaches or cloud issues. This paper focus on importance of virtualization, Related Literature, Categorization of Mitigation Techniques and Techniques to avoid threats.

Keywords: Cloud Computing; mitigation techniques; virtualization; Security Threats

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic driving force towards technological development over many years has always been the developments of internet activities. Therefore, cloud computing and virtualization technologies have provided an amicable solution to internet development in many industries and institutions with significant opportunities for organizations to reduce costs and enhance operational efficiency [1]. Cloud computing is a parasol term that is used to describe the distribute on of hosted services via the internet [2]. This form of computing allows organizations to use and employ a compute resource like virtual machines (VMs), spaces for storage or even applications the same way they would use a utility like electrical energy [3]. In particular, virtualization enables CC by encapsulating the software layer (Virtual Machine Monitor or Hypervisor) of underlying operating systems and hardware platforms to provide inputs, outputs and behaviour similar as those provided in actual physical devices [4].

From an information security perspective, virtual machines do not depend on the state of the underlying physical hardware, which indicates inherent security benefits associated with the decoupling of logical and physical states. However, the overall design, development, and implementation of

virtualization technology have also presented new security vulnerabilities and threats [5] [6]. While some of the novel security threats may not arise directly from virtualization technology, there is the risk of threats taking new forms in relation to virtualization and cloud computing. For instance, virtualization creates an environment through which reverse engineering attacks can thrive by compromising security algorithms, encryption keys, anti-bugging measures, and intrusion detection.

Furthermore, embedded technologies in virtual networks such as networking and virtual routing may have security implications including intrusion control, computer forensic processes and cyber security issues [2]. The nature form of computing brings about a new threat matrix and there is the need to look into and deal with the threats and vulnerabilities that may come up in their operational environments [7]. If these threats are not addressed, various problems like access of data by unauthorized persons may occur, derailing of services from the cloud, denial of service, attacks on hosts and even guests [8]. Threat mitigation ensures that personal data is safe and that there is no breach or stoppage of services due to the illegal access of cloud infrastructure by people who have malicious intent.

A. Significance of Threat Mitigation in Virtualized Environments

The popularity of virtualization technology among users and cloud service providers could be associated with the huge cost savings and high return on investment (ROI). Essentially, drivers for virtual environments include data centre consolidation, multi-tenancy, better server utilization, and relatively high speed of provisioning. These characteristics indicate the huge benefits of virtualization regarding reducing capital expenditures on server hardware and optimizing operational efficiency [5]. Furthermore, VMM has a characteristic resource control property, which ensures low-level visibility or introspection of VM operations. These features are essential for integrity and availability. On the other hand, these properties can be detrimental with threats targeting OSs, software running on OSs, VMs, OSs running in VMs, VMM, as well as the virtualized network environment [5].

In order to design and develop secure systems or applications, it is important to develop a threat model addressing two components: the security design elements of a virtual model and definition of possible attacks [5] [9]. This is especially important a threat and mitigation model that attempts to address all potential types of security attacks and leakage concerning all possible virtual platform configurations, using all manner of supporting software or hardware, can be too general to be of any practical use. The classic threat modeling process entails five components [9]. They are listed below: Vision, Diagram or model, Identification of threats, Mitigation measures and Validation.

Vision: Describes where an organization wants to be considering its security requirements and use cases for particular scenarios.

Diagram or model: Is the creation of a diagrammatic representation of trust boundaries.

Identification of Threats: Involves using the STRIDE element to describe potential attacks.

Mitigation measures: The mitigation component addresses how to eliminate threats via redesigning, using standards mitigations, inventing novel mitigation approaches, or accepting the risk.

Validation: The component in this model aims to ensure the accuracy of diagrams and ascertain mitigation of all the

threats.

This model allows stakeholders in a virtual network to define a vision of security requirements, communicate security design aspects of a VMM/VM system (Diagram), analyse potential security issues (Validation), discover and mitigate threats (Threat Identification), and manage mitigations for pertinent security issues (Mitigation Techniques) [9].

Based on the model presented above, enterprises need to review their existing processes and develop effective measures to address security risks inherent in their virtual and physical environments.

The remaining parts of this paper are organized as follows: Section 2 discusses some of the similar surveys. Section 3 provides the categorization of Mitigation Techniques related to virtualization.

II. RELEATED WORK

A growing body of research explores virtualization related security treats and mitigation techniques. In 2014, Bloch et al. [4] stated the emerging security threats, challenges and analysis of issues that face virtual machines in the mitigation interferences that were being faced in cloud computing. In this paper, they offered the insight into how dynamic the cloud was in its application. The authors studied various forms of cloud computing and the threat that faced each before coming up with solutions on how to deal with the risks that were posed. In this research, the security measures in dynamic data storage have not been considered to the later. In addition, the issues of fine grained data with error location should remain addressed.

In [2013], M. Pearce et al. [10] examined security issues in virtualized environments and recommends various approaches for the secure implementation of virtualization technology. The authors, tackled the framework to address various threats in virtual environments result from VMM trust models and how these threats could be dealt with. However, these authors have not discussed in detail the implications of virtualization technology on different cloud service models and measures to be taken whenever there is a security issue is not properly tackled.

In [2012] R. Martin, et al. [11] presents general mitigation strategies for side channel attacks focusing on the cloud infrastructure, but it is limited to the fidelity of fine grain timekeeping and performance counters that allows attackers to distinguish between micro-architectural events.

In [2012] Hsin-Yi Tsai et al. [12] analysed several virtualization security issues and threats in different cloud service models, but it is limited to only cloud virtualization.

In [2012] Manavi, et al. [13] offer an in-depth look into clouding and virtualization by analysing the risks and the ways in which these risks can be mitigated. However, they formed a discussion on the hierarchical secure of virtualisation and they also used literature from other experts to ensure that he has a basis to discuss the issues of cloud security and virtualization. However, this work is limited to about the risks that comes with cloud computing.

III. CATEGORIZATION OF MITIGATION TECHNIQUES

Mitigation techniques refer to the way in which various threats can be dealt with successfully to ensure that systems and businesses are protected from access that is not authorized. There are six major techniques when it comes to deal with mitigation and they are as follows: Access Control, Authentication, Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability and Non-repudiation.

The schematic diagram in figure 2 illustrates the classification of state-of-the-art mitigation techniques for virtualization related threats. Consistent with threat and mitigation model presented in figure 1, the classification of identified mitigation techniques is based on the need to protect

can join and leverage access policies as a mechanism for preventing unauthorized control.

ii. Sandboxes

On the other hand, virtual machine sandboxes, which consist of multiple programs, provide additional security in collaborative environments [8]. Sandboxing is a novel technology for combating even the most advanced threats. It operates by providing a confined or isolated space where users can download applications and programs before migrating them to the actual server. This helps to prevent malicious programs in virtual networks.

Fig. 2. Classification of Mitigation Techniques for Virtualization Related Threats

cloud computing and virtualized environments against six primary categories of attacks [14]: Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks, attacks on hypervisor, resource-freeing attacks (RFA), Side Channel Attacks, attacks on confidentiality, and other general attacks involving non-technical means.

A. ACCESS CONTROL TECHNIQUES

Threat mitigation approaches that rely on access control techniques for virtualization and related threats exploit authentication and authorization mechanisms as a strategy for verifying the identity of network entities and enforcing appropriate user privilege levels. In particular, existing literature identifies two types of access control techniques [15]: Trusted Virtual Domains (TVD) and sandboxes.

i. Trusted Virtual Domains

TVD represents a novel model for IT security. The design purpose in TVD aims to meet business goals via simplified management and provision of explicit infrastructure containment guarantees. TVD enforces access control by ensuring that only machines that meet specific requirements

B. AUTHENTICATION TECHNIQUES

The purpose of authentication is to verify that network entities are actually who they claim to be. Effective authentication in virtual networks can be achieved using three fundamental techniques: federated virtual networks, certificate-based techniques, and key-based techniques [15].

i. Federated Virtual Networks

As mentioned previously, isolation is a key security requirement in virtual networks, but virtual networks need to cooperate at a certain level. The role of federation in virtualized environments is to enable end-to-end connectivity via virtual devices.

ii. Certificate based Mitigation Approaches

Digital certificates provide a robust strategy for access control using authentication mechanisms. In [16], the authors implemented X.509 certificate for an authentication and authorization scheme with OpenNebula in FermiCloud.

iii. Key based Authentication Techniques

Similarly, key-based authentication techniques can help to prevent identity theft in virtual environments. Enforcing key-based authentication can improve system security. In particular, Secure Shell or SSH network protocol can provide a secure and encrypted communication in virtual networks. That is, SSH server can help authenticating clients using various approaches.

C. CONFIDENTIALITY PROTECTION TECHNIQUES

Data confidentiality is a primary security objective, especially in virtualized environments characterized by multi-tenancy and sharing of resources. Consequently, existing literature shows a diverse set of techniques for mitigating threats against confidentiality in virtual platforms [3] [15]. Overall, these techniques fall under four categories [15]: VLANs and VPNs, tunneling and cryptography techniques, firewalling and sub-netting, and path splitting, and introspection limiting.

i. Virtual LANSs (VLANs) and Virtual Private Networks (VPNs)

VPNs allow remote users to connect to private enterprise networks and access internal systems. VLANs can help users communicate privately and securely in virtualized environments. Combining VLANs and VPNs techniques helps in identifying packets from foreign networks and enables VLAN-connected devices to route network packets in a secure manner. The overall strategy in these techniques is to isolate untrusted physical channels from the trusted network.

ii. Cryptography and Tunneling Techniques

Tunneling techniques and cryptography play an essential role securing virtualized environments. Tunneling approaches fall into two categories. The first approach involves running tunneling software in the host system to capture packets from the physical devices and channel it towards the VMs. The second approach entails running tunneling software on the VM to restrict traffic within the virtual networks. In [3], SSH based tunneling mechanism is proposed to ensure secure access.

iii. Sub-netting and Firewalling Techniques

Using firewall and sub-netting provides additional security defences in virtual networks. In a previous study, [17] showed that indeed, firewalls, subnets, and routing tables can protect VMs from security threats such as network sniffing and spoofing.

iv. Path Splitting Techniques

Path splitting is a technique of simplifying virtual links by allowing substrate networks to split the virtual network over multiple substrate paths. Path-splitting techniques can mitigate information interception attacks in virtual routers [15]. The

last technique that mitigates confidentiality threats in virtual networks is limiting or even disabling introspection features. However, this approach introduces additional security risks because attackers could exploit it and attack VMs [15].

D. DATA INTEGRITY PROTECTION TECHNIQUES

Apart from confidentiality and availability, another goal in the CIA-triad is integrity. Techniques that mitigate security threats against data integrity in CC and virtual environments fall into three categories: cryptographic techniques, time stamping techniques, and techniques based on limiting or disabling introspection [15].

i. Cryptographic Techniques

Cryptography is a method that relies on the storage and transmission of data in a form that ensures access to those authorized to access it. In particular, cryptographic tunneling protocols can mitigate threats associated with malicious entities that manipulate messages in virtual networks. In [18], researchers identify IPSec as a viable technology for implementing secure tunnels between gateways via Encapsulating Security Payload (ESP) protocol suite.

ii. Time Stamping Techniques

The concept of trusted time stamping means monitoring the time taken to create and modify documents. Digital time stamping technology allows enterprises to enforce non-repudiation to verify application and data integrity. Analyzing patterns in IP timestamps can help in detecting VM environments without installing any program on a target machine.

iii. Limiting Introspection

Limiting introspection can prevent data tampering in virtualized environments because this functionality enables the modification of running applications in VMM. This approach minimizes security risks associated with restore operations and rollback [15].

E. AVAILABILITY PROTECTION TECHNIQUES

Availability is a basic security goal in virtual networks. In [15], the authors argue that the main strategy for maintaining network availability is to ensure proper isolation of resources and mitigating attacks against both the virtual and physical devices. The techniques for mitigating threats against availability threats in virtual networks fall into two groups: physical resources isolation approaches and techniques based on virtual network resilience.

i. Physical Resource Isolation Techniques

A major concern in virtual environments is the potential abuse of physical resources as networks attempt to optimize their performance. Exhaustion of resources can lead to network availability issues [15]. Some attacks such as DoS

attacks exploit these approached. A viable approach to solve this problem is resource isolation that allows virtual networks to enforce bandwidth reservations or resource reservations.

ii. Virtual Network Resilience

Maintaining available in virtual networks is a challenge even with physical resource isolation. The best approach is to combine resource isolation with resilient virtualization layers. Such an approach can mitigate attacks that target network performance and resources.

F. NON-REPUDIATION TECHNIQUES

Last, nonrepudiation techniques can prevent threats in virtual networks by providing evidence on malicious actions taken by various entities [15]. This security countermeasure is useful in virtual networks characterized by multi-tenancy and resource sharing. At the cloud level, [19] proposes deployment of handshake or non-repudiation enabled protocols.

IV. DISCUSSION

The investigation draws a number of insights on mitigation techniques for virtualized environments. Table 1 shows a summary of the mitigation measures addressed in various applications. It is notable that majority of the publications address access control and availability mitigation measures and techniques. This is perhaps due to the high prevalence of attacks that exploit access rights to launch attacks in virtual environments as well as attacks that aim to disrupt the availability of networks and resources in virtualized environments. Authentication, confidentiality, and integrity fall closely behind, which could be attributed to inherent security risks in virtualized environment associated with characteristics multi-tenancy and resource sharing.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The development of software and applications for use in cloud computing and virtualized environments should take into consideration potential security vulnerabilities, threats and the possible mitigation techniques. The overarching contribution of this paper is the classification of mitigation techniques in virtual networks and related environments. The mitigation methods provide users and cloud providers with various options when deploying cloud models and virtual networks. With the escalating cyber security concerns, future research should involve developing a model for detecting and preventing resilient threats to virtual networks.

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APPENDIX

TABLE 1. SECURITY MITIGATION MEASURES IN VIRTUAL NETWORKS

Publication (Reference)	Mitigation Techniques					
	<i>Access Control</i>	<i>Authentication</i>	<i>Confidentiality</i>	<i>Integrity</i>	<i>Availability</i>	<i>Non-repudiation</i>
3		*	*			
5	*					
6	*					
7	*					
8	*				*	
10					*	
15	*	*				
14						
16	*	*			*	
17			*		*	
18				*	*	
19				*	*	*